

Fostering F.A.I.R. Data and Standards in Rare Hematological Diseases

Deliverable 1.1

Project Management, Quality Assurance Plan, Risk Assessment and Contingency Plan

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Disclaimer

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Author/s	Petros Kountouris, CING Dilem Ruhluel, CING
Reviewer/s	Petros Kountouris, CING Sotiroula Chatzimatthaiou, CING Martijn Kersloot, AUMC Ronald Cornet, AUMC Fedele Duccio Bonifazi, FGB

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Table of Contents

Table of Acronyms	6
1. Executive summary	7
2. HemaFAIR project	8
2.1 Project summary	8
2.2 Reporting periods.....	8
2.3 HemaFAIR Consortium	8
2.4 Main Project Contacts.....	9
2.4.1 Coordinator	9
2.4.2 EC Project officer	9
3. Legal documents	9
3.1 Consortium Agreement (CA).....	9
3.2 Grant Agreement (GA).....	9
3.3 Supporting material.....	10
4. Work plan.....	11
4.1 WPs	11
4.2 Deliverables.....	15
4.3 Milestones	16
5. Management Structure	18
5.1 The Operational Level.....	18
5.2 The General Assembly (Consortium) Level.....	19
5.3 WP Leaders Group	19
5.4 Other roles	19
5.4.1 Task Leaders	19
6. Organisation Meetings and Procedures.....	19
6.1 Kick-off Meeting (KoM)	19
6.2 HemaFAIR General Assembly (Consortium) meetings	20
6.3 Monthly WP meetings.....	20
6.4 Designated contacts	20
6.5 Notice of a meeting.....	21
6.6 Running of Meetings.....	21
6.7 Sending the agenda	21
6.8 Adding agenda items.....	22

Project Management, Quality Assurance Plan, Risk Assessment and Contingency Plan	4
6.9 Follow-up of Meetings	22
6.10 Decisions	22
6.11 Reviewing.....	22
7. Financial Management	22
7.1 Estimated budget and EU contribution	22
7.2 Periodic reports and payments	22
8. Project Communication Strategy	24
8.1 Internal Communication Tools (ICTs).....	24
8.2 Requirement Analysis	24
8.3 Functional requirements	24
9. MS Teams Document Management and Communication Tool	25
9.1 Implementation	25
9.1.2 Channels	26
10. Mailing lists	26
11. Risk Management and Contingencies	27
12. Quality assurance plan	27
12.1 Central Documents	28
12.2 Quality Assurance Procedures for Deliverables and Reports.....	28
12.3 Naming Conventions.....	28
12.4 Version Control	29
12.5 Modification and Revision Log.....	29
12.6 Quality Check.....	29
12.7 Peer Review Process.....	30
12.8 Preventive Actions	30
12.9 Deliverable Submission	30
12.10 Quality Assurance Procedures for Publications.....	30
Appendix 1: Deliverable Template	32
Disclaimer	32
Document information	33
Version History	33
Table of Acronyms	35
1. Executive summary.....	36
2. Text and Structure.....	37

3.1 About text and titles37

 3.1.2 Recommended text font37

 3.1.3 Recommended text size37

 3.1.4 Text colour:37

3. Figures, tables and references38

 4.1 About figures, please remember to:38

 4.2 About tables, please remember to:38

 4.3 Example table formats used in this document38

4. Conclusions.....39

5. References.....40

6. Appendix41

Table of Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial intelligence
AUMC	Amsterdam University Medical Centre
CA	Consortium Agreement
CING	The Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics
CO	Coordinator
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication
Diss Level	Dissemination Level
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ECR	Early Career Researcher
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, Social Issues
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FGB	Fondazione Per La Ricerca Farmacologica Gianni Benzi Onlus
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Internal Communication Tools
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
LUMC	Leiden University Medical Centre
MS Team	Microsoft Teams
PDF	Portable Document Format
PERT	Project Evaluation and Review Technique
PM	Project Manager
PMT	Project Management Team
PROM	Patient-Reported Outcomes
PU	Public
R	Report
RD	Rare Disease
RHD	Rare Haematological Disease
SEN	Sensitive
STSE	Short-Term Staff Exchange
VHIR	Fundació Hospital Universitari Vall D'hebron - Institut de Recerca
WP	Work Package

1. Executive summary

This document aims to provide guidance on the effective management of the project from its inception. It also outlines the roles and responsibilities of each partner in the consortium and the reporting structure that will be used throughout the project. The document includes a plan for risk management and contingency plan as well as a quality assurance plan for project deliverables.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide guidance to all HemaFAIR project partners on how the major aspects of the project are managed, monitored and controlled. It does not supplement or replace the European Commission (EC) provisions or official documents, e.g., the EC Grant Agreement, nor the Consortium Agreement (CA), but summarises important information and provides links to all key documents.

2. HemaFAIR project

2.1 Project summary

HemaFAIR aims to promote multi-centre, data-driven, patient-centred research in RHDs by demonstrating the application of findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable FAIR principles to rare hematological diseases (RHD) research at national and international levels.

The objectives are:

- To implement ontology-based conceptual models, biomedical domain ontologies, genetic data standards, ontologies for reuse of human data, and other specifications for creating FAIR and artificial intelligence (AI)-ready data in RHD research
- To strengthen administrative skills and develop sustainable research management and support infrastructures in Cyprus
- To raise the research profile of researchers in Cyprus through a detailed training programme with a focus on Early Career Researchers, project managers and administrative staff

The project has 5 partners, and consists of 14 Work Packages, with 20 deliverables.

HemaFAIR is funded under Horizon Europe's Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area (ERA) programme. It is a 'Coordination and Support Actions HORIZON-CSA' aiming to enhance networking activities between research institution of the Widening countries acting as co-ordinators, and top-class leading counterparts at EU level, by linking four research institutions from four different countries.

The HemaFAIR project has started on July 1st, 2024, and it has a duration on 36 months (ending: July 1st, 2027)

2.2 Reporting periods

Reporting periods serve to divide the project into regular periods for technical reporting and monitoring.

The EC has identified two reporting periods for HemaFAIR project:

	Start date	End date	Duration
First period	01.07.2024	30.09.2025	15
Second period	01.10.2025	30.06.2027	21

2.3 HemaFAIR Consortium

No.	Organisation Name	Short Name	Main Contact
1	The Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics	CING	Petros Kountouris
2	Fundació Hospital Universitari Vall D'hebron - Institut de Recerca	VHIR	María del Mar Mañú-Pereira
3	Fondazione Per La Ricerca Farmacologica Gianni Benzi Onlus	FGB	Fedele Duccio Bonifazi
4	Amsterdam University Medical Centre	AUMC	Ronald Cornet

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5	Leiden University Medical Centre	LUMC	Marco Roos
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2.4 Main Project Contacts

2.4.1 Coordinator

Petros Kountouris, *PhD*

The Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics

Tel. +357 - 22 392623

E-mail petrosk@cing.ac.cy

2.4.2 EC Project officer

Maria Korda, *PhD, LL.M, MSc, BA (Hons)*

European Research Executive Agency Established by the EU

Unit REA.C3-Widening Participation

Please note, if you wish to contact the Project Officer, it should be done via the Coordinator and/or through the EU Participant Portal.

3. Legal documents

3.1 Consortium Agreement (CA)

The CA for HemaFAIR project is the legal contract between the partners who participate in this joint action. In the context of this Horizon Europe project involving 5 partners across Europe, a CA is necessary to ensure that all partners have a clear understanding of their rights, obligations, and responsibilities in the project.

The CA sets out the terms and conditions that govern the relationship between the partners. It covers various aspects of the project, including the roles and responsibilities of each partner, the intellectual property rights of the project, the allocation of funds and resources, the decision-making process, and the dispute resolution mechanism.

The fully executed CA for the HemaFAIR project was sent to all partners on 11 September 2024.

3.2 Grant Agreement (GA)

The GA for the HemaFAIR project is the legally binding contract between the EU and the Consortium that outlines the terms and conditions for funding. It covers various aspects of the project, such as project objectives, funding, eligible costs, reporting and monitoring requirements, intellectual property rights, ethics and data protection, and dissemination and exploitation of project results. The GA is critical in ensuring effective collaboration between the EC and the Consortium, and that the project is carried out in accordance with the EC's requirements and standards.

The complete document is available for downloading on the EU Funding and Tenders Portal (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>).

3.3 Supporting material

Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA) (version 1.0 DRAFT, 01/05/2024)

A user guide explaining all articles of the GA, providing examples and sample calculations.

EU Funding and Tenders opportunities – Online Manual

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual>

4. Work plan

The project is structured in 14 Work Packages (WPs), listed and briefly described in the following table (table 1). An up-to-date list is available in the EU Funding and Tenders portal.

The Project Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT) diagram, shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**, provides a graphical representation of the HemaFAIR project work plan.

Figure 1. PERT diagram for HemaFAIR project detailing structure and interactions between WPs

4.1 WPs

Table 1 List of WPs in HemaFAIR project.

WP No.	WP	Leader	Start (m)	End (m)
1	Project Management and Coordination (Phase 1) It regards the overall project management and operation governance.	CING	1	15
	Task 1.1 Project Management and Administration (Phase 1)		1	15
	Task 1.2 Quality Assurance and Risk Management (Phase 1)		1	15
	Task 1.3 Technical and Scientific Coordination (Phase 1)		1	15

WP No.	WP	Leader	Start (m)	End (m)
	Task 1.4 Financial and Legal Management (Phase 1)		1	15
2	Project Management and Coordination (Phase 2) It regards the overall project management and operation governance. Task 2.1 Project Management and Administration (Phase 2) Task 2.2 Quality Assurance and Risk Management (Phase 2) Task 2.3 Technical and Scientific Coordination (Phase 2) Task 2.4 Financial and Legal Management (Phase 2)	CING	16 16 16 16 16	36 36 36 36 36
3	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (Phase 1) It regards the overall plan and strategy for project output dissemination, exploitation and communication and the tools that will be used throughout the project duration. Task 3.1 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication plan and tools Task 3.2 Content Creation and Dissemination Activities Task 3.3 Multistakeholder analysis and engagement Task 3.4 Exploitation activities and IP management	CING, VHIR CING CING VHIR CING	1 1 15 15 15	15 15 15 15
4	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (Phase 2) Explains the second phase of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy of the project. Task 4.1 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication plan and tools Task 4.2 Content Creation and Dissemination Activities Task 4.3 Multistakeholder analysis and engagement Task 4.4 Exploitation activities and IP management	CING	16 16 16 16 16	36 36 36 36 36
5	Scientific Innovation Strategy and Sustainability Plan (Phase 1) It regards the development of strategies to strengthen sustainable networking between leading European institutes and CING in coordinating projects regarding RHDs and FAIR data management Task 5.1 Analysis of gaps and requirements for scientific excellence and innovation capacity Task 5.2 Scientific excellence and innovation strategy	LUMC	1 1 6	15 6 15

WP No.	WP	Leader	Start (m)	End (m)
	Task 5.3 Strategic Networking		6	15
6	Scientific Innovation Strategy and Sustainability Plan (Phase 2) Explains the processes for further development and implementation of strategies to strengthen the sustainable networking between leading European institutes and CING. Task 6.1 Monitoring of the scientific excellence and innovation strategy Task 6.2 Monitoring and updating of strategic networking Task 6.3 Long-term scientific agenda and sustainability plan	LUMC, CING LUMC LUMC CING	16 16 16 24	36 36 36 36
7	Education, training and capacity building (Phase 1) It regards the development of educational, training and capacity-building tools to aid knowledge transfer to Cyprus, and other Widening countries by the EU collaborators. Task 7.1 Analysing of training and capacity building requirements for Cyprus and beyond Task 7.2 Development of the training programme Task 7.3 Short-Term Staff Exchanges and Mentoring Programme	AUMC AUMC AUMC CING	1 1 6 1	15 12 15 15
8	Education, training and capacity building (Phase 2) Explains the second phase for the development of educational, training and capacity-building tools to aid knowledge transfer to Cyprus, and other Widening countries by the EU collaborators. Task 8.1 Implementation and monitoring of the training programme Task 8.2 Short-Term Staff Exchanges (STSEs) and Mentoring Programme (Phase 2)	AUMC	16 16 36	36 16 36
9	Strengthening of research management and administrative skills (Phase 1) It regards to the development of CING research and administrative capabilities through direct transfer of best practices from leading EU partners. Task 9.1 Benchmarking & Gap Analysis	VHIR	1 1	15 12

WP No.	WP	Leader	Start (m)	End (m)
	Task 9.2 Establishment of a project management unit at CING		3	15
10	<p>Strengthening of research management and administrative skills (Phase 2) Explains the second phase of processes for the development of CING research and administrative capabilities through direct transfer of best practices from leading EU partners.</p> <p>Task 10.1 Develop a methodology for the identification of suitable research and funding opportunities in RD and RHD</p> <p>Task 10.2 Enhancing post-award management and cross-functional team coordination</p>	VHIR	16	36
			16	24
			24	36
11	<p>Regulatory, ethical, legal and social issues (Phase 1) It regards the development and management of regulatory, ethical, legal and social (ELSI) issues during the first reporting period of the project as required.</p> <p>Task 11.1 Regulatory requirements and ELSI issues related to the project implementation</p> <p>Task 11.2 Evaluation of the current situation and identification of training gaps</p> <p>Task 11.3 ELSI and regulatory contents, including gender equality, for training</p> <p>Task 11.4 ELSI and regulatory requirements related to the use case</p>	FGB	1	15
			1	15
			6	15
			6	15
12	<p>Regulatory, ethical, legal and social issues (Phase 2) Explains the development and management of regulatory, ethical, legal and social (ELSI) issues during the second reporting period of the project as required.</p> <p>Task 12.1 Monitoring of ELSI issues related to the project implementation</p> <p>Task 12.2. Monitoring and analysis of the current situation and identification of training gaps</p> <p>Task 12.3. Monitoring of ELSI and regulatory contents, including gender equality, for training</p> <p>Task 12.4 Monitoring of ELSI and regulatory requirements related to the use case</p>	FGB	16	36
			16	36
			16	36
			16	36
			16	36
13	Use case: Demonstration of FAIRification and analysis (Phase 1)	CING, VHIR,	1	15

WP No.	WP	Leader	Start (m)	End (m)
	It regards the research component of the project where the FAIRification process will be demonstrated on two haemoglobinopathies related platforms			
	Task 13.1. Pre-FAIRification – use case design and use plan	VHIR	1	12
	Task 13.2 Implementation of patient-centred research tools	CING	9	15
	Task 13.3 FAIRification	CING	9	15
14	Use case: Demonstration of FAIRification and analysis (Phase 2)	CING	16	36
	Task 14.1 Collection of patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) data	CING CING	16 16	30 30
	Task 14.2 FAIRification – phase 2	LUMC	18	36
	Task 14.3. Post-FAIRification assessment and demonstration of data analysis and sharing			

4.2 Deliverables

Table 2 List of deliverables

WP	Deliverable Name	Leader	Type	Diss Level	Due Date (m)
1	D1.1 Project Management, quality assurance plan, risk assessment and contingency plan	CING	R	PU	6
1	D1.2 Data Management Plan	CING	DMP	PU	6
2	D2.1 Updated Data Management Plan	CING	DMP	PU	18
2	D2.2 Final Data Management Plan	CING	DMP	PU	36
3	D3.1 Project Website and social media	CING	DEC	PU	3
3	D3.2 Dissemination Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan	CING	R	SEN	6
4	D4.1 Updated DEC Plan	CING	R	SEN	24
4	D4.2 Final DEC Plan	CING	R	SEN	36
4	D4.3 Report on DEC activities	CING	R	SEN	36
5	D5.1 HemaFAIR strategy and action plan for enhancing the regional, European and international position of CING regarding creating and using FAIR data	LUMC	R	SEN	15

WP	Deliverable Name	Leader	Type	Diss Level	Due Date (m)
6	D6.1 Long-term strategic development and sustainability plan	CING	R	SEN	36
7	D7.1 Training programme description	AUMC	R	SEN	12
8	D8.1 Report on training and capacity-building activities	AUMC	R	SEN	36
9	D9.1 Methodology document for identifying suitable research and funding	VHIR	R	SEN	12
10	D10.1 Report on post-award capacity enhancement of research management and administrative skills	VHIR	R	SEN	36
11	D11.1 Set of regulatory and ELSI recommendations for the implementation of the use case	FGB	R	SEN	6
12	D12.1 Analysis of how training needs on regulatory and ELSI have been addressed	FGB	R	SEN	36
13	D13.1 FAIRified PROM modules on Cyprus Haemoglobinopathy Patient Registry	CING	Other	SEN	15
14	D14.1 Report on FAIRification of the two use case platforms	CING	R	SEN	30
14	D14.2 Report on data analysis and sharing	LUMC	R	SEN	36

4.3 Milestones

Table 3 List of Milestones in HemaFAIR project.

Milestone Name	Means of Verification	Leader	WP	Due date (m)
DEC plan approved by the Consortium	Deliverable 3.2	CING	WP3	6
Survey for scientific excellence and innovation capacity completed	Evaluation and approval by all WP leaders	VHIR	WP5	6
Requirements of training collected, analysed and shared with the Consortium	Internal report	AUMC	WP7	6
First STSE achieved	STSE report submitted to the Consortium	AUMC	WP7	6
Applicable ethical requirements to be implemented during the processing of	A statement shared with the Consortium	FGB	WP13	6

Milestone Name	Means of Verification	Leader	WP	Due date (m)
personal data identified				
Draft description of the training programme shared with the Consortium	Document shared with WP leaders	AUMC	WP7	9
Design and requirements of use case shared with the Consortium	Internal report	CING	WP13	9
HemaFAIR roadmap and schedule for participation in international events	Evaluation and approval by all WP leaders	LUMC	WP5	12
Identification of strengths and weaknesses in research management and administration	Completion of the internal benchmarking report	VHIR	WP9	12
Methodology for enhancing management and administration capacity approved and ready for implementation	Internal report	VHIR	WP9	12
Training material developed in all WPs shared with the WP7	Training material shared	AUMC	WP11,5,7,9	12
Requirements for training and regulatory and ELSI identified through surveys	Internal report with survey results identified and needs	FGB	WP14	12
First PROM response	PROM response in the registry	CING	WP14	18
Roadmap for advancing scientific excellence and innovation capacity has been implemented	Evaluation and approval by all WP leaders	CING	WP6	24
FAIRification of training material	Online repository	CING	WP6,10,8,12	24
Preliminary results of data analysis shared with the Consortium	Internal report with preliminary results	CING	WP14	30

Milestone Name	Means of Verification	Leader	WP	Due date (m)
Surveys re-launched to evaluate the short- and medium-term impact of HemaFAIR	WP6,10,8,12	CING	Survey invitation sent	33

5. Management Structure

The management structure of the HemaFAIR project is composed by three levels:

- The **Operational Level** includes the Coordinator (CO) and the Project Management Team (PMT)
- The **General Assembly Level** includes one representative of each partner institute
- The **Work Package Leaders Group** includes an assessment group of the Consortium. It shall assess the individual and overall implementation of the Project

5.1 The Operational Level

The CO is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the partners and the Granting Authority.

The Project Manager (PM) supports the CO to ensure the day-to-day project management, as well as administration and meeting logistic tasks. The members are listed in table below, including a brief description of relative responsibilities, compose the PMT.

Table 4 The details of the Operational Level Management and their roles.

Name	Role	Responsibilities
Petros Kountouris	CO representative	The CO has responsibilities to perform the tasks assigned to the leading institute as described in the GA.
Dilem Ruhluel	Project and Dissemination Manager (PM)	The PM is responsible for overall project coordination, ensuring timely delivery of project outputs and milestones, managing project risks, and ensuring effective communication and collaboration between consortium partners. They are also responsible for coordinating the communication and dissemination activities, including giving support in developing and implementing a

		communication and dissemination materials for the project, managing the project website, social media channels, and organizing project events.
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5.2 The General Assembly (Consortium) Level

The General Assembly consists of the whole project Consortium. Any member can be appointed to act as a representative in a General Assembly meeting and they will have the right to vote at the meetings attended. The Consortium as a whole is responsible for the successful execution of the project actions.

5.3 WP Leaders Group

WP Leaders Group consists of the Coordinator and WP leaders. WP leaders are responsible for the programme of work within their WP.

The work package leader role includes:

- Ensuring that the tasks and deliverables within their work package are delivered on time and to the required quality criteria and according to the budget provided
- Identifying and reporting risks and deviations within their WP to the CO and PM
- Assessing the status or completion of each WP and preparing the periodic reporting for the WP together with the CO
- Supporting the CO in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related information and deliverables
- Suggesting performance indicators for the determination of proper completion of WP to the General Assembly

5.4 Other roles

5.4.1 Task Leaders

The task leaders are responsible for the work within their task, ensuring that tasks are delivered on time and to budget, reporting any deviations from the work plan to the WP leader, for further escalation if necessary to the project CO, PM and other interested partners.

6. Organisation Meetings and Procedures

The following meetings will ensure the continuous communication between partners, efficient monitoring of project activities and timely identification of risks and contingency plans.

6.1 Kick-off Meeting (KoM)

The KoM was a crucial event for the start of the HemaFAIR project. The meeting took place in Cyprus, on 11-12 July 2024. The main purpose of the KoM was to bring together all Partners of the Consortium, to establish a common understanding of the project objectives, to agree on the work plan and deliverables, and to clarify the roles and responsibilities of each partner.

The KoM was organised by the PMT and chaired by the Project CO, who provided all Partners with relevant information about the HemaFAIR project, including any specific instructions or requirements from the EU.

During the meeting, the following topics were covered:

- Introduction of partners and project team members
- Presentation of the project objectives, including an overview of the work plan, milestones, and deliverables
- Presentations on each partner institutions research profile
- Presentations on each WPs from the leading partner institute
- Discussion on the project management structure and decision-making procedures

All meeting materials (presentation slides, agenda, photos, videos) are provided to the Partners on a shared communication tool, Microsoft Teams (MS Teams).

6.2 HemaFAIR General Assembly (Consortium) meetings

The PMT will be responsible to plan and organise annual meetings (one in-person, one virtual) every 6 months while also considering the project development activities. These events will take place;

- to summarise the progress of the project development during the preceding months
- to highlight and address potential critical issues that have emerged
- to update all Partners so that they are fully aware of the general progress of the project
- to plan the activities of the following months
- to discuss the administrative concerns, if present
- to discuss potential joint proposals, collaborative research projects
- to aid direct mentoring of CING staff and ECRs (in-person events)

In case of a request from any Consortium partners, the CO and PMT is responsible to convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any partner.

6.3 Monthly WP meetings

These online meetings will involve at least two Partners between the main beneficiaries (in terms of staff effort and competence) engaged in the development of the relative WP, including the WP leader and the HemaFAIR PM. At the beginning of the project, these will be held every month, to monitor and verify the course of the work. The WP leaders have the responsibility to schedule their respective WP progress meetings. If more frequent meetings are required, these meetings are to be scheduled by the respective WP leader as needed. The WP meetings will be held on MS Teams platform as a user-friendly, collaborative online environment.

6.4 Designated contacts

From each individual partner, a designated person (apart from the PI) will be the main contact point for any written/oral communication. The list below shows the designated persons from each institute in HemaFAIR project.

Table 5 Name of the designated contacts from each institute in HemaFAIR project.

Institute	Contact	Email
CING	Petros Kountouris (PI), Dilem Ruhluel (PM)	petrosk@cing.ac.cy dilem@cing.ac.cy
VHIR	María del Mar Mañú Pereira (PI), Maria Victoria Cerezo Morales	mar.manu@vhir.org maria.cerezo@vhir.org
FGB	Fedele Duccio Bonifazi (PI), Viviana Giannuzzi	fg@benzifoundation.org vg@benzifoundation.org
AUMC	Ronald Cornet (PI), Martijn Kersloot	r.cornet@amsterdamumc.nl m.g.kersloot@amsterdamumc.nl
LUMC	Marco Roos (PI), Eleni Mina	m.roos@lumc.nl e.mina@lumc.nl

6.5 Notice of a meeting

The CO and/or PM of the Consortium shall give notice in writing of a meeting to each member of the Consortium as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Table 6 Notice of a meeting for ordinary and extraordinary meetings.

Meeting	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
Consortium meetings	14 calendar days	7 calendar days
WP meetings	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

6.6 Running of Meetings

Within each meeting a chairperson should be assigned as well as someone to record the minutes and actions from the meeting.

- For the Consortium meetings, the chairperson will be the project CO with the PM recording the minutes and actions from the meeting.
- For WP and task meetings, the meeting should be facilitated by the WP or task leader respectively.

6.7 Sending the agenda

The PM and/or CO shall prepare and send each member of the Consortium a first version of the written agenda no later than minimum number of days preceding the meetings as indicated below.

Table 7 Calendar days limit to send the primary agenda.

Meeting	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
Consortium meetings	14 calendar days	14 calendar days
WP meetings	7 calendar days	7 calendar days

6.8 Adding agenda items

Any Member may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all the other Members no later than **7 calendar** days preceding the meeting and **2 days** preceding an extraordinary meeting. During a meeting of the General Assembly the Members present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

6.9 Follow-up of Meetings

Minutes of the meeting shall be taken by the PM and draft of the meetings should be made available no later than **10 days** after the end of the meeting. The minutes should be circulated to all parties concerned for comments or approval. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within **15 calendar days** from receipt no objection is received from the Consortium.

The minutes of the meetings will be stored on the HemaFAIR MS Teams in the 'Meetings' folder for Consortium and WP meetings separately.

6.10 Decisions

Any decision may be taken in a meeting with **51%** of agreement of all Members. A decision may also be taken without a meeting if the CO and/or PM circulates to all members of the Consortium a written document which is then agreed by the defined majority of all Members of the Consortium with a deadline for responses of **at least 10 calendar days** after receipt and the decision is agreed by **51%** of all Members.

6.11 Reviewing

The review period for each deliverable has been set up as **7 calendar days** from the day of notice. For each deliverable, a reviewing partner will be assigned considering the competencies of each partner. If any members of the Consortium are expecting to be absent during one of these review periods which would result in them being unable to fulfil their duties, they should notify the PMT in order to allow them to assign a replacement.

Review process will be comprised of a structured review with the initial version of the deliverable being created by the task leader, this is then reviewed by the WP leader after which it is passed to another WP leader (or designated person) as lead reviewer. After the final review is completed and feedback is incorporated to the deliverable, the PMT who also ensure that the documents are formatted and structured correctly, properly named and labelled is responsible from uploading the deliverable to the EC Participant Portal.

7. Financial Management

7.1 Estimated budget and EU contribution

The estimated budget for the action is € 1.499.975,25. The funding rate for costs is 100% of the action's eligible costs.

7.2 Periodic reports and payments

The periodic reporting for HemaFAIR is done using the EU Continuous Reporting portal, which is an online platform that allows for the submission of periodic technical and financial reports.

The portal is accessible through the Participant Portal, which is the central gateway for the management of Horizon Europe projects.

The reporting process typically involves the following steps:

- 1) All partners contribute to the periodic technical report and the CO prepares the final version of the periodic report and submits it through the EU Continuous Reporting portal
- 2) The report is reviewed by the EU, which may request further information or clarification if necessary
- 3) The Commission approves the report and releases the next payment of the grant

The Partners in the Consortium are informed of the outcome of the report and the payment status.

The frequency of the reporting is determined by the GA, which sets out the reporting periods and deadlines for the project. The reporting period and the relative payment timeline are shown in the following table.

Table 8 Reporting period and payment timelines.

RP No.	From	To	Duration (m)	Type	Deadline for submission (m)	Interim/Final Payment
1	01.07.2024	30.09.2025	15	Interim report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment 90 days from received periodic report
2	01.10.2025	30.06.2027	21	Final report	60 days after end of reporting period	Final payment 90 days from receiving periodic report

Table 9 Budget breakdown per reporting period (Pre-financing).

Institution	Budget as per CA	% Of total budget	Pre-financing distribution to partners
CING	€ 625,525	0.417	€344,093.75
VHIR	€221,875	0.148	€122,031.25
FGB	€221,226	0.147	€121,674.44
AUMC	€218,750	0.146	€120,312.50
LUMC	€212,500	0.142	€116,875.00
TOTAL	€1,499,976		
Pre-financing received	€824,986,94		

8. Project Communication Strategy

8.1 Internal Communication Tools (ICTs)

After careful consideration and evaluation, the PMT has selected MS Teams as the primary document management system and internal communication tool. MS Teams offers a comprehensive set of features and functionalities that align with the project's requirements, including secure file storage, version control, collaboration tools, and access management. Additionally, Google Groups is used to obtain a distribution email address for easy communication between the Consortium.

By leveraging these selected ICT tools, the project aims to enhance collaboration, streamline document sharing, and improve overall internal communication efficiency. The use of MS Teams and a group emailing list enables seamless access to project-related documents, facilitate real-time collaboration, and promote effective communication among Consortium members.

In the following sections, we will provide a detailed analysis of the project's requirements, describe the features and functionalities of MS Teams and discuss its integration to the project, and outline the training and support mechanisms to ensure successful adoption and utilization of these tools.

8.2 Requirement Analysis

The functional requirements define the specific features and capabilities that the ICT tool must possess to support efficient collaboration, document management, and project monitoring.

In this section, we will conduct a comprehensive analysis of the requirements for the ICT tool, taking into consideration document management and the integration of Google Groups mailing groups for effective email communication within the HemaFAIR project.

8.3 Functional requirements

Based on the needs of the HemaFAIR Consortium, the following functional requirements have been identified:

- *Document management.* The ICT tool should provide a platform for storing and organizing project-related documents, it should support version control, ensuring that the most up-to-date versions of documents are easily accessible while also allowing options to access the previous versions if necessary. It should allow secure file sharing among Consortium partners while maintaining appropriate access controls.
- *Collaboration and communication.* The tool should offer collaborative workspaces where HemaFAIR partners can engage in discussions, share ideas, and collaborate on documents. Real-time messaging or chat functionality could be beneficial for quick and informal communication among Consortium members.

In addition to the functional requirements, non-functional requirements outline the qualities and constraints that the chosen ICT tool should possess. These include factors related to usability, performance, security, and cost-effectiveness. Therefore, the following non-functional requirements have been identified:

- **User-friendliness:** The ICT tool should have an intuitive and user-friendly interface to ensure ease of use for all HemaFAIR participants
- **Performance and reliability:** The tool should offer stable and reliable performance, accommodating the expected user load and document storage requirements
- **Security:** The ICT tool should prioritize data security and confidentiality, implementing robust security measures to protect project-related information
- **Project tracking:** The ICT tool should allow user friendly programs to be integrated to allow simple tracking of the project deliverables

9. MS Teams Document Management and Communication Tool

By leveraging the robust features of MS Teams, the HemaFAIR project aims to streamline document management processes, enhance collaboration, and ensure the secure and efficient sharing of project-related files.

Key Feature and Functionalities

- **Version Control:** MS Teams enables users to keep track of document revisions, ensuring that the most up-to-date version is easily accessible. The version history feature allows users to review changes made to a document, restore previous versions if needed, and maintain a clear audit trail of document modifications.
- **Collaboration Tools:** MS Teams enhances collaboration among Consortium members by providing a range of collaboration features. Users can co-edit documents in real-time, leave comments and annotations. These collaborative functionalities promote efficient teamwork and streamline communication among project partners.
- **Integrations:** MS Teams integrates seamlessly with other productivity tools commonly used in research and project management, such as Microsoft Planner or Asana. This integration enables users to work with their preferred tools while leveraging Team's document management capabilities.
- **Video conferencing and chat features:** MS teams offers screen sharing, video recording, and real-time document editing features, making it easy for the partners to examine the files they need, contribute to discussions in Consortium meetings. The chat feature of the platform allows platform for informal discussions, and quick communications avoiding long email chains, in-document comments, and version control issues on documents.

9.1 Implementation

To ensure efficient document management and collaboration within the HemaFAIR project, a well-organized folder structure will be established within the MS Teams platform. This structure will facilitate easy access, version control, and seamless collaboration on project documents. The following subsections outline the proposed shared folder structure:

A private MS Teams named HemaFAIR is created, and all the project partners are provided access. Under the main HemaFAIR Teams, nine channels are created preliminarily according to the topics in project proposal. Throughout the project progress WP leaders are responsible of their respective folder organisation and documentation.

To further organize and categorize the documents within each WP folder, relevant subfolders will be created. The subfolders will help streamline document storage and retrieval, ensuring easy navigation and efficient collaboration within each WP.

Figure 2 HemaFAIR MS Teams channel distribution.

9.1.2 Channels

General project documentation can be found in the 'General' channel. For instance, the kick-off meeting materials (presentations, agenda, photos and videos), the CA, project proposal and corresponding Annexes, HemaFAIR slide template to be used in meetings, and networking events are saved in the files section of this channel. WP specific channels (Training and capacity building, use case FAIRification, Project Management and administration etc.) are added under the 'general' channel. Preliminarily, a 'deliverables' folder is added to all eight channels. The folder organisation and naming of each channel is in responsibility of the WP leaders.

10. Mailing lists

By creating operative email groups using Google Groups, the HemaFAIR project has established dedicated communication channels for efficient collaboration and information sharing. These email groups ensure targeted communication within specific entities, allowing

for focused discussions and streamlined coordination. The PMT will regularly update and maintain these email groups to ensure accurate and relevant communication throughout the project lifecycle.

Table 10 Mailing lists created in HemaFAIR project.

Group	Mailing list	Focus
General	hemafair@googlegroups.com	General communications concerning all the Consortium Project updates
HemaFAIR EU partners	hemafair-eupartners@googlegroups.com	Communications to CING partners only

11. Risk Management and Contingencies

During the implementation of HemaFAIR project, potential risks will be continuously monitored in each WP by the respective WP leaders. A list of critical risks identified during the project planning phase is provided in Annex I, Part A. However, it is important to note that unforeseeable risks may occur during the project development.

To identify and mitigate any risks or delays early, the following routine will be followed:

- 1) WP leaders will inform the CO and the PM of potential risks in their WPs
- 2) The WP Leaders Group, consisting of the CO and WP leaders, will assess the risks
- 3) The WP Leaders Group will determine the level of risk (high, medium, or low) considering its potential impact on time, quality, and costs and its probability of occurring (likelihood)
- 4) Actions addressed to affect probability and/or impact before the risk turns into an actual event (mitigation plans) will be defined prioritizing high risks, and actions to be carried out if the risk turns into an actual event (contingency plans) will be devised as well
- 5) If mitigations require significant changes to the action plan, such as major reallocation of staff efforts or budget, the CO will inform the Consortium, which will vote.
- 6) If fundamental changes to the action plan become necessary, the CO will inform the Project Officer on behalf of the Consortium, seeking advice and permission to amend the action plan.

In case of disputes, the PMT will make every effort to solve all problems amicably for the benefit of the project.

12. Quality assurance plan

All partners of the project are responsible to reach, maintain and improve the results throughout the project progress. The sections below detail the steps that are currently in place and planned to be undertaken, for the quality assurance of the project.

12.1 Central Documents

The following documents will serve as additional sources of information and will be of help to assure a continuous level of quality of the project:

- The **CA**. This agreement legally defines all aspects of cooperation between the partners of the consortium.
- The **GA**. This agreement outlines the rights and obligations as well as the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to the beneficiaries for implementing the action.

The project consortium uses several universal templates for the various project aspects. At the time of writing of this report (October 2024), the following templates have been prepared and circulated to the project partners:

- **Slide Master**. A template for all internal and external presentations that are related to the project, enabling a uniform appearance. The template contains the logo of the project HemaFAIR and the logo of the EC.
- **Deliverable Template**. A template for all report deliverables of the project, enabling a uniform appearance. The template contains the logo of the project HemaFAIR and the logo of the EC.

Other templates may be created according to the needs of the project.

12.2 Quality Assurance Procedures for Deliverables and Reports

Most deliverables are written jointly with a range of partners. To optimise the effort for handling such documents, it is important for all participants to follow agreed standards to be used in deliverable editing and exchange. Microsoft *Word*, and *Excel* are selected as standard tools in order to ensure easy access to the project documents and to reduce potential editorial burdens.

All the project documentation to be published or with an external visibility when in their final version, must be released in Portable Document Format (PDF).

12.3 Naming Conventions

It is important to follow a specific format of file naming in order to avoid losing track of their circulation. This is especially important for documents that require numerous contributions from different partners and may circulate frequently within the Consortium.

All deliverables shall be named as follows:

**[YYYY.MM.DD] _HemaFAIR_ [deliverable number (Dx.y)] _ [deliverable title] _
[version and subversion number (Vk.h)]**

Example format for the current document:

2024.08.05_HemaFAIR_D1.1_Project Management Plan_V0.1

Explanation of the placeholders:

- Dx.y= Deliverable number
 X= Number of the WP associated
 Y= Sequential number
- Vk.h= version number + subversion number (e.g., 1.0, 1.1, 2.0, 2.1)
 - Subversion numbers will be used for internal review and communication process between partners. If the first version (V0.1) of a document is reviewed by one partner, the next version will be created (V0.2). The first submission of a document to the EC should be created as V1.0. If a second submission is needed, this should be named as V2.0 etc.

12.4 Version Control

The partner responsible for a deliverable is also responsible for the control of the versions produced. He/she is the only one who can manage and update the main document.

Any updated deliverable shall be circulated to the consortium partners by uploading it in the project repository on MS Teams.

12.5 Modification and Revision Log

All deliverables shall include a Document History including the various versions and the contributions collected from the partners. The table below shall figure on the first pages of each deliverable.

Table 11 Version History of the Document.

Version	Date	Description	Contributors

12.6 Quality Check

To achieve the highest possible quality of project outcomes, all deliverables must undergo a peer review process before they are submitted to the EC. The review will consider the technical content, the objectives of the project and whether the document(s) submitted adhere to formal requirements established in the GA and CA.

The reviewers will review the documents against the following criteria:

- Technical approach
- Consistency with (a) the overall scope of the project, (b) with previous documentation, and (c) formal requirements established in the GA and CA
- Logical coherence – e.g., clear link between the methodology, results and conclusion
- Format and quality of the document(s), including layout, format, language and grammatically correct English
- The internal reviewers must provide detailed comments on the specific parts of the deliverables, particularly if changes are suggested

12.7 Peer Review Process

A Peer Review Process has been set up in order to obtain and guarantee the quality of the deliverables that will be produced during the course of the project and delivered to the EC.

All deliverables will be evaluated by two reviewers.

Peer reviewers should be nominated at least 8 weeks before the due date and communicated to the Consortium. Nominated peer reviewers can turn down the invitation with clear justification (e.g., lack of experience) and would thus be requested to be substituted with another candidate.

Consented peer reviewers are required to review the deliverable within **7 days**. In case of any expected delay, peer reviewers should notify the corresponding partner immediately. During the peer review process, peer reviewers are encouraged to discuss the problems identified in the deliverable with the partner responsible from the generation of the deliverable.

The final version of the Deliverable must be released **at least 2 weeks** prior to be delivered to EC for internal review for all partners interested.

12.8 Preventive Actions

All partners can make proposals to improve working processes, or how activities should be managed, and prevent actions that may compromise on the quality of project activities. Such actions should however be notified to the Project CO before they are taken.

12.9 Deliverable Submission

Each deliverable needs to be submitted to the EC for approval. Final acceptance of documents can only happen in a review. If project Deliverables are not accepted, the payment can be delayed. It is thus in the interest of all concerned partners that documents are produced according to the quality standards and on time.

12.10 Quality Assurance Procedures for Publications

Most publications are written jointly with a range of partners. All participants will follow agreed standards to be used in publications editing and exchange.

Microsoft Word, Excel and PowerPoint are selected as standard tools in order to ensure easy access to the project documents and to reduce potential editorial burdens.

All the project documentation to be published or with an external visibility when in their final version, must be released in an open and non-proprietary format such as Portable Document Format (PDF).

Quality check procedures for publications are similar to the those of deliverables and reports in the previous section.

In HemaFAIR project, the Consortium will follow specific measures to provide open access to publications, results and dataset while also ensuring data protection as necessary:

- The Consortium and participating partners shall individually deposit publications and their underlying datasets in an online repository
- The Consortium shall ensure immediate and full open access for all-peer reviewed publications
- The authors of each publication shall retain copyright and can seek licences to enable open access to the publications
- All contributions to the project's dataset shall be uniquely identifiable and the data shall be uniquely attributable through unique identifiers

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Appendix 1: Deliverable Template

Fostering F.A.I.R. Data and Standards
in Rare Hematological Diseases

Deliverable X.X

Deliverable name

Project Acronym	HemaFAIR
Grant Agreement No.	101159589
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01
Start date	1 st of July, 2024
Project duration	36 months

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are provided by the HemaFAIR project’s consortium under EC grant agreement **101159589** and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Document information

Deliverable No.	
Title	
Reporting Period	
Due date	
Submission date	
Work Package	
Type	
Dissemination Level	
Author/s	
Reviewer/s	

Version History

Version	Date	Description	Contributors

Table of Contents

Table of Acronyms	35
1. Executive summary.....	36
2. Text and Structure.....	37
3.1 About text and titles	37
3.1.2 Recommended text font	37
3.1.3 Recommended text size.....	37
3.1.4 Text colour:	37
3. Figures, tables and references	38
4.1 About figures, please remember to:.....	38
4.2 About tables, please remember to:	38
4.3 Example table formats used in this document.....	38
4. Conclusions.....	39
5. References.....	40
6. Appendix	41

Table of Acronyms

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1. Executive summary

Executive summary should summarise the primary headings included in the document. It should be short enough to be easily scanned by the reader but long enough to be clear and comprehensive.

The summary should be a stand-alone page; therefore, it is NOT recommended to use section numbers or WP numbers.

2. Text and Structure

3.1 About text and titles

3.1.2 Recommended text font

Tahoma

3.1.3 Recommended text size

- 11 for the main text
- **16 for the Heading 1 style titles**
- 13 for Heading 2 style titles

3.1.4 Text colour:

- 59,56,56 is the recommended text colour for the main text,
- 0,32,96 is the recommended text colour for the Heading 1
- 192,0,0 is the recommended text colour for the Heading 2

3. Figures, tables and references

4.1 About figures, please remember to:

- Always centre them on the page
- Insert figure caption below
- Caption font size should be 10pt
- Captions should also be centred on the page
- Insert the source as 'adapted from/reproduced from if the external images are used

4.2 About tables, please remember to:

Always centre them on the page and autofit to window.

- Insert table caption above
- Caption font size should be 10 pt
- Captions should also be centred on the page
- Don't forget to include the source if you insert external tables

4.3 Example table formats used in this document

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5
Text	Text	Text	Text	Text
Text	Text	Text	Text	Text

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5
Text	Text	Text	Text	Text
Text	Text	Text	Text	Text

Text	Text

Text	Text

4. Conclusions

This section should conclude the work done and outline next steps.

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5. References

For references, please use the numbering format (Vancouver) and a Reference Manager such as Mendeley to insert the citations automatically. Please ensure the reference numbering is updated in the document after addition/deletion of a reference.

Sometimes you may want to use footnotes¹ rather than references.

6. Appendix

Anything that is related but not a core part to the deliverable can go into this section.

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